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GREEN BUSINESS PRACTICES, CHALLENGES, AND PROSPECTS OF MSMEs OF A PROVINCE IN CAGAYAN VALLEY, PHILIPPINES: A DTI-SMU ENGAGEMENT FOR SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to document the green business practices and challenges of micro, small, and medium enterprises of Nueva Vizcaya and identify prospects for engagement for sustainability in collaboration with the Department of Trade and Industry. Qualitative method was used to present the green business practices and challenges encountered by mainstream business owners and managers from the food sector. Results revealed that most of the MSME-respondents are engaged in breads and pastries production and have at least two to fifty employees with an initial capitalization ranging from Php 5,000 to Php 3,000,000 and generated annual revenues/sales ranging from Php 12,000 to Php 13,000,000. MSME-respondents catered to different customers in the province and other cities and provinces and has received support from the Department of Trade and Industry, Department of Science and Technology, Department of Agriculture, and local government units, and has received awards and recognition from various government agencies. The MSME-respondents display very good practices in the reduction of power waste and energy saving despite their limited awareness and waste sorting practices. Limited knowledge of the MSMEs, weak implementation of environmental policies, and expensive cost of adopting green business practices were the common challenges encountered. The Department of Trade and Industry and Saint Mary's University can engage in conducting information dissemination campaigns to MSMEs to heighten their green business practices with emphasis on zero-waste disposal practices and product development, energy saving practices, use of eco-friendly and affordable packaging and labelling, and use of cashless transactions.

Keywords: environmental sustainability, green entrepreneurship, sustainable business

INTRODUCTION

According to Ahmad (2016), the increasing consciousness towards environment and need for sustainable economic development has led to the emergence of green business practices, with the view to minimize the detrimental impact of business on global and local environment, community, society, and economy. He further explained that green business practice includes environmentally friendly activities initiated by companies to become more sustainable. These organizations aim at reducing their harmful impact on environment through initiatives like cutting down on waste, environment protection, responsible use of scarce resources and encouraging ethical environmental practices.

An environmentally conscious business should participate at least in any of the 4Rs: Reduction, Reuse, Recycle and Recovery. Each of the "R" can be achieved through several practices,

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some of which are: using renewable and natural ingredient and products, reducing power waste, energy saving, green packing, green building, eco-cleaning, eco-labeling, less use of paper less printing, using public transport, waste sorting, spreading awareness about “green business”, and green packaging. Firms with new green business models seek to reduce costs, wastage, and environmental impacts, while also creating value with superior products and services. They redefine established production, logistics, and marketing methods, informed by green managerial practices (Haden et al., 2009). It is also supported by Nair & Paulose (2014) that becoming environmentally friendly lowers costs, because firms end up reducing the inputs they use.

In the Philippines, there are also MSMEs who are practicing green interventions. In a study conducted by Global Green Growth Institute and ASSIST Asia (2017), results show that majority of green interventions are implemented in areas of waste reduction and recycling. Also, food processing requires a good amount of thermal heat energy and energy is the major cost of processing. Energy saving and efficiency interventions, particularly in fuel switches, change of heating processes and replacement of light bulbs were noticed. Rainwater harvesting and water reuse were common interventions in saving water resources. There was only one initiative in emission reduction.

As stated in the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise Development Plan, 2017-2022, one of the strategies that need to be pursued because of its overall relevance is the promotion of green growth. This includes resource efficiency and cleaner production which are essential to competitiveness. MSMEs have to implement environment-friendly and climate-smart processes and practices to reduce production costs, produce green products and services, and prepare for the impacts of climate change (Perez, 2018).

The study will benefit the Department of Trade and Industry since they can provide assistance to MSMEs in sustaining their green business practices. Micro, small, and medium entrepreneurs will also be benefitted since they can assist DTI in the development of activities that will help strengthen their green business practices. Since there are few literatures and studies on green business, the researchers intend to document the green business practices and challenges of micro, small, and medium enterprises of Nueva Vizcaya and identify prospects for engagement for sustainability in collaboration with the Department of Trade and Industry.

METHODOLOGY

The study used the qualitative approach to present the green business practices and challenges encountered by MSMEs in the province of Nueva Vizcaya. The participants of the study were the 16-mainstream micro, small and medium entrepreneurs or managers from the food sector who received high-end intervention from the Department of Trade and Industry-Nueva Vizcaya from the beginning to the present like trainings and seminars, product development, participation to trade fairs, and facilitation of FDA application who are situated in the key municipalities of Nueva Vizcaya specifically Solano, Bayombong, and Bambang. Mainstream MSMEs located in other municipalities and not identified by the Department of Trade and Industry Nueva Vizcaya, those who did respond to the request, business which stopped their operations during the data gathering, and MSMEs which are not available due to hectic schedule were excluded from the study. Purposive sampling was used to determine the respondents of the study.

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The green business practices of MSMEs in Nueva Vizcaya were documented along the areas of usage of renewable and natural ingredients and products, reduction of power waste and energy saving, green packing, green packaging, and eco-labelling, green building, eco-cleaning, less usage of paper less printing, usage of public transport, waste sorting, and spreading awareness about “green business which was summarized by Ahmad (2016) based on various studies gathered. The challenges in the implementation of green business practices were also identified. In this study, **usage of renewable and natural ingredients and products** refers to the implementation of renewable energy resources and use of naturally grown or organic ingredients. **Reduction of power waste and energy saving** refers to the activities of the business to reduce energy waste or increase energy saving. **Green packing, green packaging, and eco-labelling** refer to the use of recyclable materials or biodegradable materials such as paper, corrugated cardboard and other forms of paper-based packaging, and green stickers in the packaging. **Green building** refers to designing and constructing the building to reduce or eliminate negative impacts on the environment and the ability of the building to generate its own energy or increase its biodiversity. **Eco-cleaning** refers to the practice of safe disposal of water waste and other harmful substances and other eco-cleaning practices applied by the business. **Less usage of paperless printing** refers to the adoption of paperless transaction to all the corporate initiatives. **Usage of public transport** refers to encouraging (or supporting) the utilization of public transport within the organization as the primary medium of business transportation, including packing, handling, and shipping). **Waste sorting** refers to the practice proper waste segregation and sorting and disposal of company waste and rubbish. **Spreading awareness about “green business”** refers to the green business initiatives of the company as part of its corporate social responsibility. **Green Business Challenges** refers to the issues and concerns related to implementation of green business identified by the entrepreneur/owner of the business. **Prospects** refer to the engagements of the Department of Trade and Industry and Saint Mary’s University in the development of activities to assist MSMEs to strengthen green business practices.

The researchers identified the green business practices of MSMEs in Nueva Vizcaya as well as their challenges through personal interview. A separate letter was also forwarded to the MSMEs for their approval to conduct the study and the informed consent form was discussed with the concerned participants before the interview started. After the permission was secured, the researchers conducted an interview containing their profile of MSMEs, green business practices, and challenges through personal interviews. Photo-documentation was done to support the responses from the interview. The data was transcribed, and the University Research Director was consulted for data analysis. Interpretation of data was done after the consultation. After analyzing the data, the results were presented to the DTI Nueva Vizcaya Provincial Office for the development of activities that will help strengthen their green business practices.

Qualitative Analysis was used to interpret the profile of the MSMEs, green business practices, challenges of MSMEs, and prospects for possible engagement with the Department of Trade and Industry. The data was analyzed thematically based on the open responses of the respondents.

To secure the respondents’ privacy, respondents’ codes were used to label data instead of using their names. Data collected were protected by ensuring that access to all confidential and sensitive data collected such as annual reports, accomplishment reports and other documents are

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managed appropriately. The participation of respondents is voluntary, and they could withdraw any time without explanation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Most of the MSME-respondents are engaged in the production of breads and pastries. MSME-respondents have at least two to 50 employees depending on the products offered and branches established. The initial capitalization ranges from Php 5,000 to Php 3,000,000 generating an annual revenue/sales ranging from Php 12,000 to Php 13,000,000 depending on the products offered, branches owned, and initial capitalization. MSME-respondents catered to different types of customers in the province and other cities and provinces and has received support from the Department of Trade and Industry, Department of Science and Technology, Department of Agriculture, and local government units in terms of seminars and training, loans, equipment, packaging and labelling of products, and marketing support. Majority of the MSME-respondents received awards and recognition from various government agencies.

Green Business Practices

1. Usage of renewable and natural ingredients and products

Among the eight bread and pastry entrepreneurs, five of them are using solar lights and panels and use LED lights/bulbs. The bread and pastry entrepreneurs also used natural ingredients coming from their own farms or from the Nueva Vizcaya Agricultural Terminal (NVAT) like bananas, cassava, carrot, squash, potatoes, sweet potatoes, desiccated coconut, and others as raw materials in the production of breads.

Figure 1. Some fresh produce utilized by the respondents in their production

For the fruit juice producer, vegetables are used like cassava, bananas, and tomatoes bought from NVAT and use vegetable oil. For the herbal tea producer, natural ingredients like turmeric, sambong, malunggay, charcoal, lagundi, and cayenne are used in the processing of herbal products while the turmeric and ginger brew producer, the members producing the products are engaged in organic farming. For the veggie noodles and chips producer, organic agricultural products used in the production are bought from the certified organic trader. For the soya sauce producer, they use lebadura (a substance used in raising bread and in making bread) specifically grass roots and sugar. For the cacao tablea

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producer, they use solar for their lights and pump. For mushroom crisps, they use rice straws, agricultural waste and saw dusts (all natural) while the taro chips producer, use taro as the main product including sweet potatoes, bananas, and cassava.

Figure2. Utilization and maximization of agricultural wastes in the mushroom production business

Generally, few of the MSMEs in the province use renewable energy resources in the form of solar lights and panels and use LED lights/bulbs while majority of them are using naturally grown ingredients available in their own farm or from the Nueva Vizcaya Agricultural Terminal in the production of their products.

As cited by Čekanavičius et al. (2014), greener businesses base their activities on the standard of environmental sustainability, minimize the damaging environmental impact of their operations, and strive to utilize renewable energy resources. It is also supported by Smith (2013) that green business can be defined as business practices that are viewed as environmentally sound, including the use of organic and natural products to build factories provide protection against emissions and environmentally friendly sourcing of materials.

2. Reduction of power waste and energy saving

Among the eight bread and pastry entrepreneurs, six of them are using power saving mode for appliances and food manufacturing equipment, refrain from using electricity if not necessary, water pump is not used to reduce electric consumption, reduce appliances i.e. from 2 refrigerators and 2 freezers to 1 refrigerator and no freezer and use of inverters for appliances and equipment.

For the fruit juice producer, solar power is used in machines to reduce energy consumption. For the veggie noodles and chips producer, equipment are used during production activity only or when there is an order. For the turmeric and ginger brew producer, the computer is not used when not needed, lights are turned off when not needed and electric fuse box is switch off during weekend. For the soya sauce producer, they do not use electric stove to save energy. For the mushroom crisps producer, they use furnace (pugon) in drying the substrates while the taro chips producer practice reduction of electricity since they do not have solar panels.

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Figure 3. Simple production machineries that are operated as-needed

Generally, most of the MSMEs in the province regardless of the product have common practices in the reduction of power waste and energy saving specifically on reducing electric consumption by not using the lights, machine, appliances, or equipment when not needed and thinking other ways like using furnace (“pugon”) in drying the substrates and reducing equipment to minimize electric consumption.

This is supported by Global Green Growth Institute and ASSIST Asia (2017) wherein a case study was conducted about MSMEs in the food processing industry showing that energy saving and efficiency interventions, particularly in fuel switches, change of heating processes and replacement of light bulbs were noticed.

3. Green packing, green packaging, and eco-labeling

All bread and pastry entrepreneurs practice green packing, packaging, and eco-labeling such as use of food grade plastics given by the Department of Science and Technology (DOST), use of brown paper and paper based packaging, use of corrugated cardboard for large scale order, encourage the use of eco-bags, use of printed labels than stickers, use of cake boxes with handle.

Figure 4. Various biodegradable packing and packaging supplies for product selling

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For the fruit juice producer, paper-based packaging is used for juice and use foil pouch bag. For the herbal tea producer, entrepouch (paper pouch) and Donewell plastic bottles, corrugated cardboards are used. The label use photo-sticker. For the veggie noodles/ chips producer, label is printed and not stickers and use of cardboard in the delivery. For the turmeric and ginger brew producer, plastic bottles and sticker papers are used. However, biodegradable plastic and brown paper are also used. Corrugated cardboards are used for orders in far areas. For the soya sauce producer, emperador light bottles are recycled and use as packaging and stickers are used as labels provided by the Department of Trade and Industry. For the mushroom crisps producer (focusing on mushroom), polyethylene materials as fruiting bags that can stand the heat during steaming and drying are used. Paper packaging is not also advisable since the product is highly perishable. Corrugated boxes are used in the final packing upon delivery. Sticker paper coming from the Department of Trade and Industry is also used as label. For the taro chips producer, foil pack in the packaging is used to preserve the freshness of the product. The label is already embedded in the foil pack.

Figure 5. Finished products displayed at various distribution stores

Generally, most of the MSMEs in the province have good practices such as the use of brown paper and paper-based packaging, use of corrugated cardboard for large scale order, and label either printed or photo sticker. There are still some who are using plastic bottles and foil packs while a certain entrepreneur used recycled Emperador light bottle.

The study of Beattie (2021) revealed that many companies are focused on reducing packaging waste. For example, reducing the use of packaging materials means lower spending, and improved fuel efficiency also helps with the company's budget. Case in point, Walmart keyed in on packaging through its zero-waste initiative, pushing for less packaging throughout its supply chain and for more of its packaging to be sourced from recycled or reused materials.

4. Green building

Majority of the respondents who are engaged in bread and pastry production have varied practices in green building such as considering that it is earthquake-proof building, designed to be open for proper lighting and ventilation to minimize the use of lights and aircon, plan the use of water collection system for rain water, presence of clean drainage system and sufficient ventilation, use of water waste filtration as recommended by the LGU and presence of chimney for the emission of smoke.

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Figure 6. Picturesque store façades complying to eco-friendly business environment.

For the herbal tea producer, the building is FDA requirement compliant while for the Taro Chips producer, it has been visited by the FDA for monitoring. For turmeric and ginger brew producers, the door and the windows are open to maintain proper ventilation and to minimize the use of aircon. For the cacao tablea producer, the area is open and has proper ventilation. For mushroom crisps (now mushroom), the design and process of production is properly planned specially with the presence of toxins like ammonia, so it must be properly disposed and the presence of grow house for the mushrooms. For the fruit juice, veggie noodles and chips, and soya sauce producers, the building is not designed to eliminate the negative impacts of the environment.

Figure 7. Store interiors and fixtures channeling proper (air) ventilation and natural (solar) lighting

Generally, most of the MSMEs in the province have good practices in green building such as planning for the proper lighting and ventilation to minimize the use of lights and aircon, presence of clean drainage system and use of water waste filtration, and planning for the design and process of production specially with the presence of toxins like ammonia and the presence of grow house for the mushrooms.

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5. Eco-cleaning

All bread and pastry entrepreneurs have varied practices in eco-cleaning such as the use of environmental cleaning products, disinfection and sanitation in cleaning before opening and after closing, used oils are brought to the farm and will serve as fertilizer, unsold breads are used as breading or converted to “pudding”, presence of drainage system and water collection system for rain water, use of stainless steam to minimize water wastage, and not using insecticides in cleaning the area.

For the fruit juice producer, the pulp (sapal) of lemon and calamansi are used to clean the comfort room while for the herbal tea producer, the pulp (sapal) is used as natural fertilizer. For turmeric and ginger brew producers, the water used to wash the raw materials and others are thrown since the water is abundant in the mountain. For the soya sauce producer, the unsold soy sauce is eaten by pigs or thrown in the soil. For the taro chips producer, the taro peelings are disposed under a pit. For the cacao tablea and mushroom crisps (mushroom) producers, they observe zero waste.

Figure 8. Lemon and calamansi pulp are used to clean the comfort room.

Generally, most of the MSME-respondents have good practices in eco-cleaning such as the use of environmental cleaning products, disinfection and sanitation in cleaning before opening and after closing, used oils are brought to the farm and will serve as fertilizer, unsold breads are used as breading or converted to “pudding”, presence of drainage system and water collection system for rain water, use of stainless steam to minimize water wastage, and not using insecticides in cleaning the area, the pulp (sapal) of lemon and calamansi are used to clean the comfort room and used as a natural fertilizer.

6. Less usage of paperless printing

Among the eight bread and pastry entrepreneurs, six of them believed that their transaction is still on paper, and it is needed in government projects and issuance of official receipts while the other two already, although they issue receipts but they already accept payments through GCash.

All other MSME food producers (fruit juice, herbal juice, veggie noodles/ chips, turmeric and ginger brew, mushroom crisps, and taro chips producers) are already accepting gcash as a mode of payment and some of the products are available in Shopee. Soya sauce and cacao tablea producers still believe in the use of paper for the issuance of official receipts.

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Generally, most of the MSME-respondents practice paperless printing through accepting payment through Gcash and selling products through Shopee.

Figure 9. Commonly adopted payment modality among MSME respondents

7. Usage of public transport

Among the eight bread and pastry entrepreneurs, four of them use their own vehicles or outsource vehicles for delivery services while the other four display their products in the store and do not have delivery or the orders are picked-up by resellers or customers.

Figure 10. Finished products displayed at the Nueva Vizcaya Pasalubong Center

For the fruit juice producers, for bulk orders, delivery is done but for minimal orders, this will be delivered through public transport. For the herbal tea producer, Shopee picked up the products and for bulk orders these are sent through a public transport. For the veggie noodles and chips, there are buyers who pick up and there are times that they hire delivery vans for the delivering to customers. For the turmeric and ginger brew producers, vehicles are used or sometimes picked up. The field staff are asked to bring their products with them for delivery. For soya sauce and cacao tablea producers, the buyers are the ones coming to them except for soya sauce producers that participates in through trade fairs. For the mushroom crisps (mushroom), sellers directly pickup the products or it is course through the organic trader. For the Taro Chips producers, commute during delivery or send products via bus for deliveries outside the province.

Generally, most of the MSME-respondents prefer to use their own vehicles or maybe picked up by the customers rather than to use public transport.

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8. Waste sorting

All of the bread and pastry entrepreneurs practice waste sorting such as proper segregation of waste, have their own proper disposal process, presence of composting pit, conversion of biodegradable waste (i.e. egg shells) as fertilizer, tin cans and pails are sold or sometimes given back to the supplier and discounts will be provided by the supplier, bad orders are eaten by chicken, dogs, or fishes and unsold salt bread (pandesal) or toasted breads are used as bread crumbs or breading, and used oils are reused as gas for the stove.

All other MSME food producers (fruit juice, herbal juice, veggie noodles/ chips, turmeric and ginger brew, soya sauce, cacao tablea, mushroom crisps, and taro chips producers) have good practice in waste sorting such as proper segregation of waste, vegetable peels are used as fertilizer or being grinded and use as soap, bad orders, spoiled breads are brought to the farm as food for the livestock, presence of garbage bins, maintaining composting pit for biodegradable, and excess ginger is converted to ginger sauce or ginger cookies.

Figure 11. Waste disposal compliance: All organic substrates (left) and garbage bins (left)

Generally, most of the MSME-respondents practice waste sorting by properly segregating their waste, have their own proper disposal process, presence of composting pit, conversion of biodegradable waste (i.e. egg shells, vegetable peels, cacao waste) as fertilizer, tin cans and pails are sold or sometimes given back to the supplier and discounts will be provided by the supplier, bad orders are eaten by chicken, dogs, or fishes and unsold salt bread (pandesal) or toasted breads are used as bread crumbs or breading, used oils are reused as gas for the stove, bad orders, spoiled breads are brought to the farm as food for the livestock, presence of garbage bins, maintaining composting pit for biodegradable, and excess ginger is converted to ginger sauce or ginger cookies.

9. Spreading awareness about “green business”

The bread and pastry entrepreneurs spread awareness about green business by conducting tree planning activities, engage in organic farming, use of biodegradable packaging and labelling, lesser use of non-biodegradable materials, encourage customers to bring their own eco-bags in support to the LGU and compliance to proper waste sorting of garbage waste.

All other MSME food producers (fruit juice, herbal juice, veggie noodles/ chips, turmeric and ginger brew, soya sauce, cacao tablea, mushroom crisps, and taro chips producers) spread awareness about green business by conducting tree planting activities,

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avoid burning waste, schedule clean-up drive in the community, use biodegradable, organic and toxin-free materials and use of all-natural raw materials that is eco-friendly.

Generally, most of the MSME-respondents spread awareness about green practices by conducting tree planting activities, lesser use of non-biodegradable materials, encourage customers to bring their own eco-bags in support to the LGU and compliance to proper waster sorting of garbage waste, avoid burning waste, schedule clean-up drive in the community, use biodegradable, organic and toxin-free materials and use of all-natural raw materials that is eco-friendly.

Challenges in the Implementation of Green Business Practices Encountered by MSMEs in Nueva Vizcaya

The following are identified challenges in the implementation of Green Business Practices Encountered by MSMEs in Nueva Vizcaya

GREEN BUSINESS PRACTICES	CHALLENGES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION
1. Usage of renewable and natural ingredients and products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Few MSMEs in the province use renewable energy resources in the form of solar lights and panels and use LED lights/bulbs. ➤ Expensive costs of using solar panels (huge kilowatt consumption in the production process) ➤ The solar application does not adopt in the solar integration of NUVELCO. ➤ Increasing prices of natural ingredients/raw materials ➤ Assistance to farmers in the disposal of fruits and vegetables.
2. Reduction of power waste and energy saving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Limited knowledge of MSMEs in the reduction of power waste and energy saving.
3. Green packing, green packaging, and eco-labeling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Expensive and costly implementation and adoption of eco-friendly materials. ➤ Limited funds to undertake other eco-friendly initiatives ➤ Lack of assistance and training in the development of attractive packaging and labelling ➤ Use of eco-bag ordinances are not strictly implemented by the LGU.
4. Green building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Few MSMEs do not consider the design and construction of the building to eliminate the negative impacts of the environment. ➤ Limited knowledge on the adoption of green building. ➤ Few MSMEs rent their buildings which limits them to design their own building.
5. Eco-cleaning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Limited knowledge of MSMEs in the adoption of eco-cleaning practices.
6. Less usage of paperless printing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Too many documents to comply in the government agencies requirements. ➤ Limited knowledge on cashless transactions.

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7. Usage of public transport	➤ Most of the MSME-respondents practice prefer to use their own vehicles and pickup the products rather than to use public transport.
8. Waste sorting	➤ Garbage collection schedule is not followed. ➤ Better intervention to solve the problems on garbage waste collection.
9. Spreading awareness about "green business"	➤ Limited initiatives in spreading about green business.

Prospects for Possible Engagement with the Department of Trade and Industry through the Development of Activities that will help Strengthen their Green Business Practices

As cited by Yang and Feng (2008), partnership building is a core process for establishing green businesses. Having partners who are aware of the environment or helping them develop corporate social responsibility is a step toward sustainability. In the realization of establishing green businesses in the province, the following are prospects for possible engagement with the Department of Trade and Industry through the development of activities that will help strengthen their Green Business Practices.

GREEN BUSINESS PRACTICES	POSSIBLE ENGAGEMENT WITH DTI
1. Usage of renewable and natural ingredients and products	➤ Conduct Training on Product Development on Oversupply of naturally grown ingredients (in collaboration with DTI, LGU, DA, and DOST) ➤ Conduct training on the promotion of organic (in collaboration with DENR, DOST, DTI and DA)
2. Reduction of power waste and energy saving	➤ Conduct info dissemination on the energy saving practices (in collaboration with DTI and NUVELCO) ➤ Develop infomercial on energy saving tips (in collaboration with DTI)
3. Green packing, green packaging, and eco-labeling	➤ Encourage LGU to give due incentives to entrepreneurs who are compliant to zero-plastic usage (in collaboration with DTI) ➤ Assist entrepreneurs in sourcing out eco-friendly and affordable packaging and labelling materials (in collaboration with DTI) ➤ Conduct information dissemination and empower entrepreneurs on the use of eco-friendly and affordable packaging and labelling (in collaboration with DTI and LGUs, DOST, and DENR) ➤ Create a Coffee table book on green packaging and labelling of local entrepreneurs (in collaboration with DTI)
4. Green building	➤ Assist entrepreneurs in food safety regulatory requirements i.e. FDA-LTO, FDA-CPR, HALAL, and HACCP (c/o DTI)
5. Eco-cleaning	➤ Conduct of Advocacy on Zero-Waste disposal practices (in collaboration with DTI, DOST, DENR and LGU)
6. Less usage of paperless printing	➤ Conduct of Advocacy on the use of cashless transaction/practice digital economy or payment (in

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	collaboration with DTI)
7. Usage of public transport	➤ Integrate topics on the usage of public transport in the green economic development training.
8. Waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Conduct of Advocacy on 7S for Entrepreneurs (in collaboration with DTI) ➤ Conduct training on Product development (i.e. vegetable peel) in collaboration with DTI) ➤ Conduct of Advocacy on Zero-Waste disposal practices (in collaboration with DTI, DOST, DENR and LGU)
9. Spreading awareness about "green business"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Conduct a forum inviting entrepreneurs with best practices in green business (in collaboration with DTI) ➤ Conduct training on green economic development (in collaboration with DTI)

CONCLUSION

This study has described and documented the green business practices and challenges of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) of Nueva Vizcaya and identify prospects for engagement for sustainability in collaboration with the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) through the development of activities that will help strengthen their green business practices. The researchers therefore conclude that based on the responses of the MSMEs or managers, most of the MSME-respondents are engaged in breads and pastries production and have at least two to fifty employees with an initial capitalization ranging from Php 5,000 to Php 3,000,000 and generated annual revenues/sales ranging from Php 12,000 to Php 13,000,000. MSME-respondents catered to different customers in the province and other areas and has received assistance from the Department of Trade and Industry, Department of Science and Technology, Department of Agriculture, and local government and has received awards and recognition from various government agencies. MSME-respondents in Nueva Vizcaya display very good practices in the reduction of power waste and energy saving despite their limited awareness and waste sorting practices and further awareness and practice on the following green business practices specifically on usage of renewable and natural ingredients and products; green packing, green packaging, and eco-labeling; green building; eco-cleaning; less usage of paperless printing; usage of public transport; and spreading awareness about "green business". Limited knowledge of the MSMEs, weak implementation of environmental policies, and expensive cost of adopting green business practices are the common challenges encountered. The Department of Trade and Industry and Saint Mary's University can possibly engage in conducting information dissemination campaigns to MSMEs to heighten awareness and practice on the green business practices with special emphasis on product development of waste materials, energy saving practices, use of eco-friendly and affordable packaging and labelling, zero-waste disposal practices, use of cashless transactions/practice digital economy or payment and organizing forum inviting entrepreneurs with best practices in green business.

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RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers therefore recommends that the government agencies (i.e. DTI, DA, DOST, DAR, and LGU) shall continue their assistance to MSMEs in terms of financing, equipment, and business-related trainings (i.e. packaging and labelling) for them to be more competitive and to gain recognition and awards. It is also suggested that mechanisms for incentives or awards can be provided to MSMEs to encourage them to adopt green business activities. Strict implementation of environmental laws is highly suggested. The Department of Trade and Industry is recommended to tap the academe (i.e. Saint Mary's University) and other government and private agencies (DENR, DA, NUVELCO, DOST, and LGU) and conduct information dissemination campaigns to MSMEs to intensify awareness and practice on the green business practices with special emphasis on product development of waste materials, energy saving practices, use of eco-friendly and affordable packaging and labelling, zero-waste disposal practices, use of cashless transactions/practice digital economy or payment and organizing forum inviting entrepreneurs with best practices in green business. It is also recommended that they include in their plan ways to reduce the cost of adopting green business (i.e. packaging and labelling). Saint Mary's University is recommended that they organize activities that will promote green business awareness and practices in collaboration with the Department of Trade and Industry and other government and private agencies as part of its environmental program. The MSMEs can be invited as beneficiaries to further adopt and strengthen their green business practices. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies in other industries or using other relevant variables.

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